

A salvaged work of art returns to architecture

First re-installation within the framework of the Art in Architecture Preservation Project

(press release)

These days, the first re-installation of a work of art that was saved as part of the Art in Architecture Preservation Project took place. The metal grille, which was saved from liquidation, was newly installed in the garden of the mansion of Mr. Nathaniel Filip de Aras in Staré Ždánice, the Czech Republic. It is regularly open to the public on various occasions. The nearest possibility is the Open Garden Weekend on June 7th and 8th, 2025.

The grille, by an unknown artist, was probably created in the 1970s or 1980s as part of the state program "percentage for art", when it was common for 1-4% of the budget for construction or reconstruction to be devoted to the artistic representation of architecture. We believe the grille served as a decorative filling for a glass door in one of the spa houses in Františkovy Lázně. We think so, because it was discovered here and bears the motif of bubbles and water.

The grille was discovered by Mr. Ladislav Zeman, a member of the *Ošklivá architektura* (in English Ugly Architecture) group. The project leader, Mr. Jan Lochman, contacted him, took over the grille, documented it, and offered it to others.

The Art in Architecture Preservation Project is dedicated to preventive and intervention activities: it protects works of art in public spaces, negotiates with owners, and finds new locations for endangered objects. So far, five works have been saved by our efforts. Others have secured the rescue in five other cases based on the project's initiative.

Unlike traditional GLAM or private collectors, the group aims to return these works to architecture and public spaces. The rescued works include, for example, a ceramic relief by Lubomír Šilar or printed tiles by Stanislav Holý. Selected works are offered for re-installation via the project website or personal contact.

Glossary

The Art in Architecture Preservation Project – is one of Jan Lochman's follow-up projects based on the Ugly Architecture group. The project was launched in 2020, when Jan Lochman took on the task of saving a ceramic relief in Prague. The work was professionally removed and is now housed in a museum. Since then, ten more works of art have been saved – either with the funds of the founder himself or thanks to the activities of related group members. Recently, the project has increasingly focused on preventive activities and finding ways to return the saved works to architecture and public space. The works offered for re-installation are on the website:

https://osklivaarchitektura.cz/Nab%C3%ADdka_um%C4%9Bn%C3%AD_pro_ve%C5%99ejn%C3%BD_prostor

The grille from Františkovy Lázně – is a salvaged metal work of art that probably comes from one of the spa houses in Františkovy Lázně. It consists of four rods connected at regular intervals by square metal plates with a plastic decor composed of circles. The motif resembles water lilies or bubbles, perhaps referring to the local healing springs. The material is probably an aluminum alloy that was electroplated and then coated with black paint. The lattice weighs 12.5 kilograms and was found in a significantly damaged condition. The rods were broken off, the surface bore traces of shear friction and abrasions, probably due to forced dismantling.

Nathaniel Filip de Aras – is a Czech chansonnier, teacher, and public figure who, through his work, continues the tradition of educated people with a broad social outlook. Since 2019, it has been reconstructing the former residence of the Ždánice millers, which was devastated during the totalitarian era. It organizes concerts and other cultural events in the newly restored villa. At the same time, it is improving the surrounding garden where this grille was located. The castle organizes regular cultural events and tours of the castle, including the garden. Link to his website:

<https://nathanielfilip.cz/>

Ugly Architecture – a project founded in 2018 by Jan Lochman aimed to popularize post-war architecture through an open dialogue between supporters and opponents of the so-called socialist modernism. Initially, Jan Lochman traveled around the Czech Republic, photographed architecturally interesting buildings, and published information about them in a Facebook group of the same name. Gradually, other people joined, and they began to notice what was around them. They began to evaluate these buildings, discuss them, and share them further. In May 2025, the project's Facebook group had 43 thousand members and 6 thousand followers. Link to the website:

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/OsklivaArchitektura>